

Fieldwork Dataset by Prof. Igor Calzada **for *Data & Policy* Article**

Description / Abstract

This dataset was compiled and curated by Prof. Igor Calzada and supports the article “*The Illusion of the Web3 Decentralization*” (submitted to *Data & Policy*). It presents qualitative fieldwork data collected between 2022 and 2025 on selected Web3 projects. The dataset aims to support scholarly examination of decentralization claims in Web3 infrastructures, contributing to debates on algorithmic governance, platform cooperativism, and anticipatory regulation.

Keywords

Web3, decentralization, digital sovereignty, blockchain governance, algorithmic power, platform cooperativism, urban AI, digital citizenship

Author

Prof. Igor Calzada
Full Professor in Interdisciplinary Digital Citizenship (Unibasq/R3)
University of the Basque Country (UPV/EHU)

Date of Data Collection

2022–2025: Based on fieldwork in Silicon Valley since August 2022 and engagement with scholars and practitioners up to June 2025

ITERATION	DESCRIPTION	DATA
1. STANFORD	This research, grounded in ongoing fieldwork action research since August 2022, from the Stanford DAO Workshops 2022 and 2023 held by the Decentralization Research Centre (DRC).	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=mTT0tCix43E
2. DRC	Participation in Decentralization Research Center's activities, particularly focusing on multistakeholder governance and infrastructure debates across decentralized technologies.	https://thedrcenter.org/2025-decentralized-tech-summit/
3. PROJECT LIBERTY AND DRC 2025	The last iteration entitled 2025 Decentralized Tech Summit took place in April 2025 in Washington DC by being held by the DRC and Liberty Project at the Georgetown University and National Press Club on 1 st and 2 nd April, following April 2024 event held by the DRC.	https://www.projectliberty.io/news/how-can-data-cooperatives-help-build-a-fair-data-economy https://thedrcenter.org/2025-decentralized-tech-summit/
4. RGS-IBG DIGITAL TERRITORIES REGIONAL FUTURES ERC	Presentation at the Royal Geographic Society RGS-IBG Annual International Conference in London, contributing to the Digital Territories theme under the ERC-funded Regional Futures project.	https://www.regionalfutures.org/all-outputs/rgs-cfp2024
5. SOAM	Engagement with SOAM residence programme in Germany, a decentralized sustainability platform advocating for ecological governance through blockchain infrastructures.	https://soam.earth/
6. BLOCKCHAINGOV ERC	Research linkage with the European Research Council project BLOCKCHAINGOV, exploring blockchain governance models, legitimacy, and legal frameworks.	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/865856/results
7. EUI	Participation in the European University Institute's Global Governance Programme project on post-Westphalian decentralisation and Web3 sovereignty.	https://globalgovernanceprogramme.eui.eu/project/new-network-sovereignties-the-rise-of-non-territorial-states/libertarian-decentralised-web3-map-in-search-of-a-post-westphalian-territory/

8. EDGE ESMERALDA	Observation and ethnographic fieldwork at EDGE Esmeralda gatherings fostering innovation and decentralized community building practices.	https://www.edgeesmeralda.com/
9. DRC Team	Collaboration and affiliation as a fellow with the Decentralization Research Center, contributing to collective research outputs.	https://thedrcenter.org/fellows-and-team/igor-Author/
10. METAGOV	Monitoring and engagement with Metagov's research on modular governance protocols for online communities and DAOs.	https://metagov.org/
11. LIBERTY PROJECT/DATA COOPERATIVES	Follow-up with Liberty Project initiatives on data cooperatives through participatory events and policy dialogues.	https://plpopup0007.splashthat.com/
12. IMPACT EVALUATOR RESEARCH RETREAT 2025, ICELAND	Participation in the 2025 Impact Evaluator Research Retreat (IERR) in Iceland, focused on metrics and epistemologies of evaluation in decentralized ecosystems.	https://www.researchretreat.org/ierr-2025/

Data Availability Statement (for Data & Policy journal)

The fieldwork data supporting the findings of this article are openly available in SSRN at [DOI placeholder]. This dataset, compiled by Prof. Igor Calzada, includes structured qualitative entries on Web3 platforms analysed in the article. It is released under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International (CC BY 4.0) license, enabling reuse with appropriate attribution.
